

Efficiency of transfer of energy from gamma irradiated crystalline potassium chloride in the oxidation of iodide ions in aqueous iodide solution

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Abstract : Oxidation of iodide takes place when the stored energy in the form of color centers is released during dissolution of γ -irradiated crystalline potassium chloride in aqueous potassium iodide solution. Various parameters like dose, amount and storage time of irradiated potassium chloride which control the yield of iodine have been studied. Similarly, the effect of concentration of potassium iodide has been investigated. The energy transfer parameter has been determined as the ratio of G/I_2^- obtained by the addition of irradiated crystalline potassium chloride on the basis of oxidation of iodide.

Keywords : Irradiation, F-centre, reduction, yield.

Introduction

Crystalline potassium chloride on exposure to ionizing radiation produce F centers and hole centers. Dissolution of such crystals in water results in the formation of hydrated electrons.

Recombination of hydrated electrons with the hole centers at the water-solid interphase during the dissolution process lead to the emission of visible light termed as aqua luminescence (AL)¹.

On the other hand the solution of crystalline potassium chloride in aqueous iodide^{2,3,14,15} and their mixtures^{4,5} induces oxidation and reduction reactions respectively.

The present paper deals with the effect dose, mesh number, storage time of irradiated crystalline potassium chloride and on the concentration variation of potassium iodide.

Experimental

AnalaR grade polycrystalline potassium chloride was sealed in a glass envelop and wrapped in black paper. This sample was irradiated to a dose of 41 kGy using a ⁶⁰Co source, whose dose rate measured by Ficke dosim-

eter was 30.24 kGy/h. The irradiated crystalline potassium chloride were dissolved in 0.1 M potassium iodide solution. The dissolution was carried out on a freshly prepared 10 cm³ aqueous potassium iodide solution of known concentration under constant stirring and in total darkness. The yield of iodine in the sample solution as well as in blank was estimated by Shinn's method⁶ measuring the absorbance at 354 nm on Hitachi spectrophotometer.

Fig. 1 shows the yield of iodine as a function of the amount of irradiated KCl added. The yield of iodine in-

Fig. 1. The plot of the yield of iodine as a function of amount of irradiated KCl.

increases with increase in amount of irradiated KCl added before it levels off above 3.0 g. Freshly irradiated samples of 3.0 g KCl were stored for various periods and then dissolved in 10 cm³ of 0.1 M KI solution.

Fig. 2 shows the yield of iodine as a function of storing time of irradiated KCl. The yield of iodine becomes

Fig. 2. The plot of the yield of iodine as a function of storing time irradiated KCl.

independent of storage time after 6 h. Fig. 3 shows the yield of iodine as a function of mesh number of irradiated KCl. The plot shows an increasing trend with decreasing mesh number of the irradiated salt.

Fig. 3. The plot of the yield of iodine as a function of mesh number of irradiated KCl.

The yield of iodine as a function of dose absorbed by crystalline potassium chloride is shown in Fig. 4. The yield of iodine increases initially with dose and becomes independent of dose above 40 kGy. The plot of the yield

Fig. 4. The plot of the yield of iodine as a function of dose absorbed by irradiated KCl.

of iodine as a function of concentration of aqueous potassium iodide solution is shown in Fig. 5. The yield of iodine increases with increasing concentration of potassium iodide. However, the nature of the concentration dependence curve of KI reveals that in the first step of concentration range ($1 \times 10^{-4} - 1 \times 10^{-2}$) M of KI, the yield of iodine is very slow. A sharp increase in the yield of iodine is observed in the second step above 0.01 M of iodide. However, the yield of iodine remains constant at about 1 M of iodide in the third step.

Discussion

The dissolution of irradiated crystalline potassium chloride in aqueous iodide solution produces iodine as the stable product. Therefore, the mechanism proposed for the conversion of iodide to iodine based on the reaction suggested by Daniels⁷, Hart⁸ and Rabini⁹ who explained the formation of iodide in their radiolysis and photolysis studies.

The following reactions are envisaged during the dissolution of irradiated salts in aqueous iodide solution.

Thus one molecule of iodine is produced at the cost of two hole center.

Concentration dependence :

The variation in the yield of iodine as a function of concentration of aqueous potassium iodide is shown in Fig. 5. The concentration curve for aqueous potassium

Fig. 5. The plot of the yield of iodine as a function of concentration of KI solution

iodide solution shows that in the first step of concentration range (10^{-4} to 10^{-2}) M potassium iodide the yield of iodine is very low. A sharp increase in the yield of iodine is observed in the second step above $0.01 M$ iodide. However, the yield of iodine remains constant at about $1 M$ of iodide in the third step. The light emission process and the oxidation of iodine complete at low potassium iodide concentrations. The net result is that a very small increment in the yield of iodine is observed up to $10^{-2} M$ potassium iodide concentration. The yield of iodine reaches a plateau above $10^0 M$ potassium iodide, indicating that this concentration of iodide is just sufficient to remove all the F-centers released during the dissolution. The yield of iodine increases when the concentration of potassium iodide is in the range of 10^{-3} to $10^0 M$. Similar conclusion were made by Gopinathan¹⁰ while studying the light emission process in aqueous iodide solution by pulse technique found (90 + 10)% quenching of light emission at $10^0 M$ potassium iodide solution.

Effect of dose absorbed :

The effect of dose absorbed by crystalline potassium chlorides on the yield of iodine showed a rapid increase in the yield of iodine (Fig. 4) up to 40 kGy followed by saturation at higher doses. According, to Gordon and Nowick¹¹ the formation of F-centers in crystalline potassium chloride is a two stage process. The initial first stage is attributed to the trapping of electrons by negative ion vacancies intrinsically present in the crystal, while second stage arise due to the generation of new negative ion vacancies during irradiation. The plateau region corresponds to the slow formation of new vacancies. The

iodide yield vs dose curve (Fig. 4) clearly indicates that the vacancies created at higher doses have no effect on the yield of iodine.

Amount, storage time and mesh number of the irradiated salt :

The yield of iodine increases with the amount of the irradiated salt added up to 3.0 g of KCl/10 cm³ iodide solution (Fig. 1). The concentration of color centers increase with increasing mass of the salt exposed to a fixed γ -dose. The yield of iodine reaches a plateau at which solubility of potassium chloride in water approaches a saturation value at room temperature. This behavior is in accordance with the observation made on the rate of the dissolution of the irradiated NaCl single crystal in aqueous NaNO₃ solution by Kalkar and Bhujbal¹². According to them the dissolution follows preferentially diffusion controlled path than activation controlled if large amount of salt is already present in the solution.

It is well known that some of the color centers in freshly irradiated crystalline potassium chloride are unstable and recombine giving room temperature luminescence⁶ (RTL). Once the RTL is over the stable color centers remaining trapped in the crystal lattice are responsible for inducing chemical changes during dissolution in aqueous solution. The yield of iodine is less for crystal in which, the RTL has completely decayed than with the freshly irradiated crystals. Moreover, the RTL can be regenerated by exposure to visible light. Hence crystalline potassium chloride are not exposed to light even during the dissolution process. The study of the yield of iodine as a function of storage time of irradiated

crystalline potassium chloride is in good agreement with the above theory (Fig. 2).

The particle size of the irradiated crystalline potassium chloride decreases on grinding. The total surface area of the salt exposed to fresh solution during dissolution process also increases with increasing mesh size of the salt. The probability of large number of color centers released instantaneously on dissolution and encountering reaction with iodide ions increases with the decreasing particle size of the salt as shown in Fig. 3. Similarly the density of the defect centers is greater at the surface than the bulk of the crystal. The cumulative effect is that there is a tendency of increased oxidation of iodide ions with the decreasing particle size of crystalline potassium chloride.

Efficiency of energy transfer :

In order to find out the effect of efficiency of energy transfer it is necessary to know the G -values of iodide for direct radiolysis of aqueous potassium iodide solution and that obtained by dissolution of irradiated crystalline potassium chloride in iodide. The value of $G(I_2)$ salt is maximum at 0.5 M potassium iodide concentration. Hence $G(I_2)^-$ as determined by radiolysis of 0.1 M potassium iodide is 0.62. The radiolysis of aqueous 0.1 M potassium iodide solution was carried out to evaluate $G(I_2)^-$. The plots of the yield of iodine vs dose is shown in Fig. 6. The $G(I_2)^-$ values determined from slope of linear plot is 0.62. The percentage efficiency of energy transfer (Φ) and the concentration of reducing species is determined at various doses absorbed by KCl salt.

Fig. 6. Radiolysis of 1 M aqueous KI solution.

The plot of percent efficiency vs dose absorbed is shown in Fig. 7. The Φ values decreases sharply up to 30 kGy dose and then become independent of absorbed dose.

Fig. 7. The plot of percent efficiency parameter vs dose absorbed by KCl.

The radiolytic product is produced at a higher rate up to 30 kGy. Prolonged irradiation has no effect on radiolytic product of KCl. Naturally the efficiency of energy transfer becomes independent of the energy stored in irradiated crystalline potassium chloride. It is interesting to study the behavior of KCl salt with the help of variation in the percent efficiency of energy transfer with dose in which the G value obtained by γ -radiolysis remains constant. The following empirical relation between reciprocal of percent efficiency (Φ) and absorbed dose is proposed to find the limiting efficiency transfer for a particular salt or phosphor.

$$(1/\Phi) = (1/\Phi_0) + kD \quad (4)$$

where Φ_0 is the limiting efficiency as the dose tends to zero, Φ is the percent efficiency at a particular dose (D) and k is a constant. The plot of the reciprocal of percent efficiency vs dose absorbed by KCl salt is shown in Fig. 8. The intercept on Y-axis gives the limiting efficiency of transfer for oxidation of iodine as 17.4%. The low value of limiting efficiency of energy transfer indicates that all the color centers produced in crystalline potassium chloride are not completely utilized to produce

Fig. 8. The plot of reciprocal of percent parameter vs dose absorbed.

iodide. The color centers are destroyed by other side reactions such as

The total concentration of color centers per mole of potassium chloride salt was obtained from the yield of iodine. The concentration of color centers in single crystal of alkali halide has been determined by physicist in the past¹³.

The concentration of defects initially present in potassium chloride salt is evaluated from the above graph by back extrapolation. The concentration of inherent color centers are found to be 1.2×10^{17} in potassium chloride.

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